

Erythrina afra Coastal Coral Tree

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 9-12 m.

Distribution:

It is a subtropical tree that occurs in the warm and frost-free to light frost coastal regions of the Eastern Cape and northern KwaZulu-Natal, but it is a popular statement tree due to its beautiful canopy and flowers and is now wide-spread throughout South Africa. It has been introduced internationally as well.

Importance:

The Coastal Coral Tree is cherished for its warm red to burnt-orange flowers, blooming from winter to spring. Popular for its easy cultivation and long flowering period, it is an ideal garden plant, admired by botanists, horticulturists, and nature lovers. With a round, spreading canopy and light green foliage, it thrives in coastal and windy conditions. The tree attracts birds with its nectar and fruit and is used in traditional medicine for anxiety, inflammation, wound healing, and infections.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 42.15 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 28.87 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.74 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 85.4%, Duplicated: 14.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 33 723.14 kilobases

Contig number: 322

Sample Contributor contact details:

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